

Plan Overview

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

Title: ERC AdG NoisyFluid. n. 101053472

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Template: ERC DMP

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Project abstract:

Fluids, in complex regimes, show random features. The aim of this project is approaching several questions around the randomness of fluids by means of a theory that could be called "Stochastic Fluid Mechanics". The distinctive feature of this theory, opposite to others that investigated the stochastic features of fluids, is that it is based on the usual continuum mechanics equations, in particular the Navier-Stokes and Euler equations, but suitably modified by the presence of random elements, like an additive or a transport type noise. Stochastic equations of fluid dynamics have been studied already for three decades and the number of foundational results is very large. However, two basic directions have been explored only partially:

- a) the origin and the form of noise in fluids
- b) the consequences of the presence of noise.

This project will make progresses in these two directions, describing the noise near boundary due to vortex productions, including the question of intrinsic stochasticity at the boundary, the propagation of additive noise at small scales to a transport-stretching noise at large scales, the consequences of transport noise on eddy viscosity, enhanced dissipation, enhanced coalescence, and other applications in turbulence and Geophysics.

The most ambitious core of the project is putting together these pieces in a picture that explains the mechanism of regularization by noise for the 3D Navier-Stokes equations. The additive noise

at small scales is responsible for a transport-stretching noise at larger scales which could prevent blow-up of high intensity vortex structures. We have already proved recently that a noise, of transport type only, has this regularization effect, but stretching amplifies vorticity and new progresses are needed to cope with both processes. We aim to use the experimentally observed fact that small scale velocity should be approximately orthogonal to vorticity in high intensity regions.

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Summary

Project Acronym

NoisyFluid

Project Number

101053472

Provide a dataset summary

From the viewpoint of data, the research performed in the project starts from previously published literature and develops mathematical computations and results reported in detail in the products of research of the project, which are in all cases open access papers (or perhaps books in the future). In a few cases, numerical simulations contribute to obtaining the final results. Let us discuss these three datasets in more detail.

Concerning the literature on which the research is based, this literature is always quoted in the papers produced by the project and it is too wide and diversified to be reported or collected here. It is literature from the fields of Probability, Stochastic Analysis, Fluid Mechanics, published in international journals or in books, available in usual university libraries or online. In all cases it is possible to find the reference on Google Scholar and often to download the paper. Thus the literature on which the works are based is transparent and detectable. A selected list of references of the full project, beyond the complete lists given at the end of each paper, will be prepared at the end of the project. For the time being, selected elements of this literature are stored in a Dropbox folder of property of the Pi, for future reference.

Concerning the products of the research, namely the papers, in all cases they are first uploaded on the repository "arXiv" <https://arxiv.org/> and then submitted to journals and, when accepted, published open access, following the rules of ERC AdG projects. All the ideas, computations and results are described in detail in these papers open to the scientific community and are reproducible by reading these papers. Until now, from the beginning of the project, I have produced 6 manuscript submitted for publications:

- 1) [Franco Flandoli](#), [Silvia Morlacchi](#), [Andrea Papini](#), Effect of Transport Noise on Kelvin-Helmholtz instability, submitted for publication on Proceeding STUOD Conference, state: under revision, see repository [arXiv:2303.00033](#)
- 2) [Franco Flandoli](#), [Dejun Luo](#), [Eliseo Luongo](#), 2D Smagorinsky type large eddy models as limits of stochastic PDEs, submitted, see repository [arXiv:2302.13614](#)
- 3) [Franco Flandoli](#), [Ruojun Huang](#), Noise based on vortex structures in 2D and 3D, submitted to J. Math. Phys., state: under revision, see repository [arXiv:2210.12424](#)
- 4) [Franco Flandoli](#), [Ruojun Huang](#), [Andrea Papini](#), Turbulence enhancement of coagulation: the role of eddy diffusion in velocity, accepted by Physica D, see repository [arXiv:2209.14387](#)
- 5) [Franco Flandoli](#), [Dejun Luo](#), On the Boussinesq hypothesis for a stochastic Proudman-Taylor model, submitted, see repository [arXiv:2304.11798](#)
- 6) [Franco Flandoli](#), Francesco Russo, Reduced dissipation effect in stochastic transport by Gaussian noise with regularity greater than $1/2$, [arXiv:2305.19293](#)

Concerning the numerical simulations, they entered into 1 and 4 above. The numerical procedures and results are reported in those papers. The numerical codes are available on the repository "Zenodo", for the time being under request (due to activity of perfecting) and soon in cc-by licence. The links are

- a) <https://zenodo.org/record/8074376> (corresponding to paper 1 above) with Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8074376>
- b) <https://zenodo.org/record/8063469> (corresponding to paper 4 above) with Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8063469>.

FAIR data and resources

1. Making data findable

As described above, the data related to the project can be summarized as: i) previous literature; ii) papers (or books) produced by the project; iii) numerical simulations.

In order to find the literature, one may consult the paper produced, where the literature is always described in detail, and find such literature also online, for instance by means of Google Scholar.

In order to find the papers produced by the project, they are available on the repository "arXiv", at the page

<https://arxiv.org/search/?query=flandoli&searchtype=all&source=header>

and also on the Project web page (the personal web page of the PI)

<https://sites.google.com/sns.it/franco-flandoli/erc-products>

All of them will be published open access. In arXiv all papers have received the arXiv identifier ([arXiv:2303.00033](https://arxiv.org/abs/2303.00033), [arXiv:2302.13614](https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.13614), [arXiv:2210.12424](https://arxiv.org/abs/2210.12424), [arXiv:2209.14387](https://arxiv.org/abs/2209.14387), [arXiv:2304.11798](https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.11798), [arXiv:2305.19293](https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.19293)) and, once published, the publisher will assign DOIs to them. These persistent identifiers support the findability of the papers.

In order to find the structure of the numerical codes and the results of the numerical simulation, they are available in the papers (see 1 and 4 of the list above). The codes are available on the repository "Zenodo" with Doi identifies

(<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8074376> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8063469>) and are provided with documentation.

When it is part of the journal policy, mention to ORCID identification of the authors is made in the presentation of the papers, mostly in the online versions.

2. Making data openly accessible

All manuscripts are openly accessible on arXiv, see

<https://arxiv.org/search/?query=flandoli&searchtype=all&source=header>

and

<https://sites.google.com/sns.it/franco-flandoli/erc-products>

and will be published open access when accepted by journals.

All numerical codes are available under request on Zenodo and described their by suitable documentation, while the results of the simulations are also described in the corresponding papers on arXiv. In Zenodo, they will be openly accessible under a CC-BY license soon.

3. Making data interoperable

Manuscripts are written in English and describe the results by standard mathematical language. The literature is written in extended form hence easy to find on the web.

Numerical codes are written with software R and in C. Documentation is provided in the submitted versions on Zenodo.

4. Increase data reuse

No embargo will be applied. All data will remain indefinitely open access. The data will remain accessible on arXiv and Zenodo under CC-BY licence and one publication sites provided by the journals.

5. Allocation of resources and data security

The cost for publication open access of

3) [Franco Flandoli](#), [Ruojun Huang](#), Noise based on vortex structures in 2D and 3D, submitted to J. Math. Phys., state: under revision, see repository [arXiv:2210.12424](https://arxiv.org/abs/2210.12424)

is around 3.500 euros.

The cost for publication open access of

4) [Franco Flandoli](#), [Ruojun Huang](#), [Andrea Papini](#), Turbulence enhancement of coagulation: the role of eddy diffusion in velocity, accepted by Physica D, see repository [arXiv:2209.14387](https://arxiv.org/abs/2209.14387)

is around 2.500 euros.

During the preparation of paper, before it is released, the partial versions of the manuscript are stored on Dropbox and constantly backed-up. The access to the full Dropbox folder is of the PI only, sharing specific subfolders of each paper with the authors of that paper.